

Data-driven comparison of federated learning and model personalization for electric load forecasting

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Federated learning and model personalization for electric load forecasting.
- Model training in accordance with relevant data privacy regulations.
- Analysis of the influence of the source data on model performance.
- Propose *Differential Comparison* method to reduce source data influence on performance.
- Statistical comparison of performance of different model training methods.

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ABSTRACT

Residential short-term electric load forecasting is essential in modern decentralized power systems. Load forecasting methods mostly rely on neural networks and require access to private and sensitive electric load data for model training. Conventional neural network training aggregates all data on a centralized server to train one global model. However, the aggregation of user data introduces security and data privacy risks. In contrast, this study investigates the modern neural network training methods of federated learning and model personalization as potential solutions to security and data privacy problems. Within an extensive simulation approach, the investigated methods are compared to the conventional centralized method and a pre-trained baseline predictor to compare their respective performances. This study identifies that the underlying data structure of electric load data has a significant influence on the loss of a model. We therefore conclude that a comparison of loss distributions will in fact be considered a comparison of data structures, rather than a comparison of the model performance. As an alternative method of comparison of loss values, this study develops the "differential comparison". The method allows for the isolated comparison of model loss differences by only comparing the losses of two models generated by the same data sample to build a distribution

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of differences. The differential comparison method was then used to identify model personalization as the best performing model training method for load forecasting among all analyzed methods, with a superior performance in 59.1 % of all cases.

Abbreviations

BASE	Baseline method
CENT	Centralized method
DT	Decision tree
FCNN	Fully connected neural network
FL	Federated learning
FedAvg	Federated averaging
FedSGD	Federated stochastic gradient descent
GDPR	General data protection regulations
LCL	Low Carbon London
LSTM	Long short term memory network
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error
PS	Personalized method
RF	Random forest
TCN	Temporal convolutional network
SOTA	State of the art
SVM	Support vector machine

1. Introduction

The widespread roll-out of smart meters is underway among residential and industrial customers as part of the transition to a decarbonized electricity system. In Switzerland, for example, the ‘Energy Strategy 2050’ mandates that 80 % of end customers will be equipped with smart meters by the end of 2027 [1]. Digital tools such as smart meters make it possible to access vast data sources to improve the performance and visibility of power grids, and to more effectively integrate renewable energy resources, thereby supporting global climate objectives and decarbonization.

One key technology enabled by the roll-out of smart meters is end-user load forecasting. Load forecasting describes the process of predicting the future power usage (grid load) of an end user or a collection of end users. It is a fundamental requirement in improving the reliability and efficiency of the electric power system as it allows utilities to predict the power required to maintain the demand and supply equilibrium [2], manage excess power consumption and production, design and implement dynamic pricing contracts, and manage network services [3].

Load forecasting is usually achieved by utilizing modern ML methods to analyze historic data streams, such as past power usage, weather forecasts, temperature measurements, etc. These data streams, with high temporal and spatial granularity, facilitate advanced forecasting methods, enabling the load forecasting of individual customers, as well as helping to improve forecasts at the aggregated level [4,5]. Fig. 1 shows a forecasting example, using five days of load data input (blue) to predict the next two days of end user load (green) compared to the actual load (orange).

The nature of electric load forecasting differs according to the intended purpose, in particular in relation to the forecasting horizon of the predictor [6]. The classes of load forecasting types that exist are [2]:

- Long Term Forecasting (longer than a year)
- Mid Term Forecasting (for a week to a year)
- Short Term Forecasting (up to a week)
- Very Short Term Forecasting (less than 24 h)

The operation and optimization of the power system most often requires a day-ahead forecast [7]. Day-ahead forecasting is therefore typically used as the time-horizon for a Short Term Forecast in power system applications.

Load forecasting can also be differentiated according to the voltage level where it is applied and the way in which load data is aggregated. Typically, load forecasting at high and medium voltage levels uses aggregated load profiles, whereas forecasting at the low voltage level, particularly at the end-customer level, requires individual load profiles. Such individual forecasts are inherently more volatile and sensitive to the behavior of the respective end-user [5]. Significant research has been undertaken in recent years to improve the performance of load curve prediction at the aggregate and individual level. However, it has been observed that traditional forecasting techniques designed to forecast load profiles at the aggregate level may not achieve satisfactory accuracy when applied at the individual level [5].

1.1. Key problem I: Data privacy

Conventional methods for accessing and analyzing smart meter data rely on data centralization and aggregation. Centralization introduces data security and data privacy vulnerability [8]. Federated learning (FL) and model personalization (PS) have been proposed as training method alternatives to avoid data centralization, and solve the data sensitivity issues posed by centralized training. Both of these methods are able to train a neural network with decentralized load curve data without infringing data privacy regulations, for example the GDPR that has been implemented within the EU.

1.2. Key problem II: Data variance

While various studies have analyzed the respective performance of FL and PS, previous work has mostly compared their performance using distributions of losses generated by p-norm loss functions such as mean absolute error (MAE). This disregards the variance in structure and scale between different data sources (i.e., the grid end users, in the case of electric load forecasting). Specifically, the differences between the structure and scale of different individual data sources make it difficult for a single model to capture all the different data structures of all data sources [9]. This may lead to significantly different error values across models, even though those models may yield predictions with a comparable level of accuracy. When selecting a best solution method, it could therefore be possible to draw an incorrect conclusion on the optimal model that is based on a difference in data structure, rather than the difference in actual model performance itself.

2. Related work

This section discusses previously published papers and experiments that have dealt with the topic of load forecasting. First, the state of the art (SOTA) for neural networks used in load forecasting is explained, considering network architectures and operating principles. Second, the SOTA research on training method alternatives, such as FL and PS, is outlined.

2.1. Model architecture

Historically, load forecasting has been performed using conventional ML approaches, such as the support vector machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), and random forest (RF). However, improvements in hardware capabilities and an increase in computational resources

Fig. 1. Example of short-term electric load forecasting. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(including at the edge) resulted in a surge in the usage of neural network. Neural networks have shown promising capabilities in learning the underlying load data structure and have therefore experienced a significant growth in development and research [4].

For time series forecasting, more modern neural networks utilize specialized model architectures to consider the temporal dimension of the source data, allowing a model to learn seasonal and repetitive behavior more easily, thus increasing model performance. Most commonly, this is achieved with either convolutional or recurrent network structures [10].

Several studies analyzed and compared the performance of different model architectures and are relevant to this work. [4,10,11] analyzed more traditional ML methods, including SVM, RF, DT, and fully connected neural network (FCNN) for load forecasting, and compared them to modern deep learning techniques such as long short term memory network (LSTM) and a one dimensional convolutional network, called the temporal convolutional network (TCN) [4] or the DeepEnergy Network of [11] respectively.

[4,10,11] all agree on the promising performance of the convolutional networks for the task of load forecasting, as they individually observed superior behavior from the DeepEnergy or the TCN networks respectively, when compared to other neural network architectures. Additionally, [4] concluded that the TCN architecture not only produced convincing performance when applied to load forecasting tasks, but that it also achieved a significant improvement during network training, as it is not as prone to the exploding/vanishing gradient problem as recurrent neural network structures. The TCN architecture is visualized in Fig. 2.

2.2. Federated learning

Several papers have discussed methods for training prediction algorithms that use decentralized data rather than centralized data, thereby improving the viability of model training given the constraints imposed by data privacy laws. The main strategy discussed in these papers is federated learning (FL). FL trains a centralized model by aggregating model weights (instead of load data) from individual consumers. Each client model is partially trained on the respective behavior from each end-user. All aggregated model weights are then combined in a node-wise averaging step to build a new and improved centralized model. This process is repeated until model convergence is reached.

The authors of [13] analyzed FL in the context of load forecasting. They conducted experiments using smart meter data from the Pecan

Street Inc's data port site [14], comprising approximately 800 homes. They evaluated and compared the performance of both centralized and personalized LSTM models in federated settings. Their results showed that federated learning is a promising approach that has the potential to create high performing models with a significantly reduced networking load compared to a centralized model, while preserving the privacy of consumption data.

[9] analyzed and compared two sub classes of the federated learning strategy to a conventional centralized ML approach, namely federated averaging (FedAvg) and federated stochastic gradient descent (FedSGD). FedAvg uses weight averaging between all FL clients to build the centralized model, whereas FedSGD averages a gradient vector of all FL clients to update the centralized model via gradient descent. They showed that FedAvg outperformed FedSGD in terms of mean absolute percentage error (MAPE).

[15] investigated FL to improve the sensor fusion for machinery fault diagnostics while preserving data privacy. They concluded that FL is a good alternative to preserve data privacy. However they address a shortcoming of FL, namely that most studies assume that the source data of each client is independent and identically distributed, which is not the case for most industrial applications. This is also known as the domain shift problem. To address this issue, they propose a federated transfer learning method to exchange distributions of client data, to achieve transfer learning across all FL clients, without communicating sensitive data from client to client.

Federated learning is also used in many other industrial sectors. [15] uses FL for the sensor fusion of intelligent machinery fault diagnostic. In healthcare federated learning is used on Electronic Health Records by [16], and [17] uses FL for improved phishing email detection.

2.3. Model personalization

[13,18] both investigate model personalization as an alternative to FL. Model personalization is the decentralized re-training of a model on just the local data source. Both studies independently conclude that model personalization on one client has a beneficial effect on the model performance, while preserving data privacy. Furthermore, model personalization solves the domain shift problem, as model personalization does not have the assumption of independent and identically distributed data across all clients.

Within the energy sector model personalization has been used successfully by [13] to improve the performance of very-short-term load forecasts of CENT and FL models. Similarly, [18] used PS to securely

Fig. 2. Neural network architecture of temporal convolutional network layer [12].

train and improve personalized end-to-end speech recognition models on mobile devices, under the constraint that the user data never leaves the mobile device and is not stored on any central server.

2.4. Loss functions

Loss functions are differentiable functions used to quantify the correctness of a prediction or classification to initiate the gradient descent process. Different loss functions measure different metrics, resulting in different network optima. Conventional load forecasting loss functions are p-norm error functions that essentially evaluate the mean distance between the target and prediction such as the Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

When used for load forecasting, p-norm loss functions suffer from the common problem that they are easily influenced by outliers and peaks in the data structure [19]. Therefore, conventional p-norm methods are not suitable for predicting peaks due to the double penalty of an incorrect prediction of a peak and that any successful forecast method requires a degree of flexibility in the temporal positioning of the peaks. In practice, P-norm loss functions tend to predict a moving-average of the target function. However, predicting the presence of load peaks is crucial for the safe and reliable operation of the power grid, and hence important for a load forecasting model, even if the exact location in the temporal dimension may be shifted moderately.

[20] therefore developed the adjusted error as a customized loss function for volatile and noisy data. It allows for a degree of flexibility in the temporal dimension when comparing the prediction and target function, effectively incentivizing the model to predict peaks. This is achieved by allowing permutations in the temporal dimension between the target and prediction within a limited number of time steps. This effectively reduces the penalty imposed on time shifted peaks.

2.5. Contributions of this paper

This study aims to evaluate the usability of both FL and PS in comparison to two conventional methods for neural network training, namely the centralized method (CENT), and the baseline method (BASE). The CENT method trains a centralized predictor on aggregated load data, whereas the BASE method invokes a pre-trained centralized predictor and employs it for decentralized data. An overview of the functionalities of all training methods included in the comparison of this study is visualized in Fig. 3. All four mentioned training method are explained in further detail in Section 3.

In addition, this study aims to identify the most suitable method for the task of end user electric load forecasting, with sufficient statistical relevance. To achieve this, the method of “Differential Comparison”

was developed to reduce the effects of the individual data structure differences on the respective loss values. Both the data variance problem and the “Differential Comparison” are further described in Section 5.1.

More specifically, the contributions of this study are four-fold:

- Firstly, this study combines the advantages of existing load forecasting methods of [4,10,20]. In particular, this study utilizes the neural network architecture described in [4,10] and combines their findings with the “adjusted error” proposed by [20] to improve the capability of a TCN network to predict stochastically distributed peaks.
- Secondly, this paper expands the research of [9,13] by investigating their proposed modern ML methods of FL in combination with the neural network architecture proposed in [4,10].
- Thirdly, this study conducts extensive simulation efforts to compare FL and PS to the conventional training methods of CENT and BASE in a statistically relevant manner.
- Lastly, this study addresses the problem of comparing model performances under the different data constraints. This is addressed by proposing the method of “differential comparison” as a more robust alternative to the commonly used averaging of losses. It is achieved by isolating and comparing the individual data samples of the different training methods from the data structure.

2.6. Structure of this paper

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows:

Section 3 contains a detailed description of the different training methods used to train the selected model within this study. It explains why the modern training methods of FL and PS are needed for end user load forecasting in the context of data privacy, and shows their conceptual difference to the conventional methods of BASE and CENT.

Section 4 describes the process used to compare the different model training methods. It contains a description of the pre-processing that was employed, provides an outline of the simulation process, and presents a hypothesis of the simulation outcome.

Section 5 describes the simulation results. Section 5.1 outlines the problem of the data bias that was observed during loss computation. Section 5.2 presents the alternative method of “differential comparison” to compare model losses generated and Section 5.3 details the results of applying the differential comparison. Lastly Section 5.4 features a summary of the results and selects the best fitting training method for the task of end user load forecasting.

Lastly, Section 6 provides a conclusion of the findings of this paper.

Fig. 3. Working principle of investigated training methods (BASE, CENT, PS, FL).

3. Model training

This section discusses the different model training methods that were analyzed within this study.

3.1. Motivation for modern model training methods

Load forecasting using neural networks entails training of the models with the respective user data. To achieve this, conventional training techniques collect and aggregate the training data at a centralized point to train one global model. This conventional training has two major downsides when it comes to load forecasting of individual end user load curves.

- The first is the sensitive and private nature of load curve data, which introduces both security and privacy risks [13] when transmitting the training data to a centralized node. Additionally, this transmission of private data may conflict with data privacy laws, such as the general data protection regulations (GDPR) in the EU.
- The second is the large variance in data structure between individual data sources. This variance increases the chances of the global model over-fitting on a subset of households. A single model may face difficulties capturing all the different data structures of all data sources [9], while the scale difference between different datasets can lead to significantly different error (loss) values of similarly accurate predictions. This is also known as the domain shift problem.

Therefore this study discusses the methods of federated learning and model personalization as training method alternatives to solve or lessen the downsides posed by the conventional neural network training methods.

3.2. Alternative I: Federated learning

FL is a method that not only enables the (re-)training of deployed models, but also the training of a centralized model with decentralized

data without actually transmitting the source data. This is achieved by training the model locally and exchanging only locally optimized model weights instead of the source data (Fig. 4). The transmitted and aggregated models are then combined in the FL server (FL-S) to build a new and improved version of the centralized model, which now includes updates from previously unknown data sources of the decentralized FL clients (FL-C).

3.2.1. Security of federated learning

FL allows clients to leverage the data streams of different clients, while retaining the data privately and safely within local storage. This is an important distinction from the conventional centralized method, as no private user data is transmitted to a central point. In practice the security of FL methods can even be enhanced further by encrypting the transmitted model weights [21].

3.2.2. Update strategies of federated learning

Several model update strategies exist in federated learning. The most common strategies are federated averaging (FedAvg) [9] and federated stochastic gradient descent (FedSGD) [9,22–24]. FedAvg creates a new centralized model by averaging all the weights of round r from all C clients in a node-wise fashion (Eq. (1)).

$$\theta_{r+1}^S \leftarrow \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{n_c}{C} \theta_r^c \quad (1)$$

Alternatively, FedSGD aggregates and averages the gradients of the different decentralized models. Various variations of FedSGD exist; however, the most popular implementation of FedSGD essentially describes a mini-batch stochastic gradient descent, where in each iteration n randomly selected stochastic gradients ∇_r , from all clients C of round r are evaluated in parallel to update the parameters θ^S of the server FL-S, where α is the learning rate of the update step (Eq. (2)).

$$\theta_{r+1}^S \leftarrow \theta_r^S - \alpha * \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{n} \nabla_{r,i} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4. Weight update of federated learning algorithm.

Based on the research results of [9,22–24], the FedAvg model combination strategy was selected for the federated learning algorithm of this study. The FL algorithm with the chosen FedAvg model averaging strategy is further described in pseudo code in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Federated learning with FedAvg

r_{max} : max. round number, C : all clients in network, S : FL Server, n : number of randomly selected clients per FL round, E : epochs, J : error, L_{Adj} : adjusted loss, θ : neural network weights, ∇ : gradient, α : learning rate, θ_0 : saved model weights

```

S.init() // Initialize server S
for each client in C do
  client.load_data()
  client.init_model(\theta_0)
  client.connect(S)
end
while round r < r_max rounds do
  Select n random clients C_n
  for e in E Epochs do
    \theta_r^c \leftarrow \theta_r^S // Receive server weights
    for client c in C_n Clients do
      X, Y = c.data.get_batch(e)
      \hat{Y} = c.model.predict(X)
      J(\theta_r^c) = L_{Adj}(Y, \hat{Y}) // Loss function
      \theta_{r+1}^c = \theta_r^c - \alpha * \nabla(J(\theta_r^c)) // Back propagation
    end
    S \leftarrow \theta_{r+1}^c // Send weights to server
  end
  \theta_{r+1}^S = \sum_{c=0}^n \frac{n_c}{n} \theta_{r+1}^c // Node wise averaging of all weights of n
  client
  r = r + 1
end

```

3.2.3. Federated learning and the domain shift problem

Federated learning has one major shortcoming: it has the impractical assumption that the data of all clients is independent and identically distributed, due to its averaging step during the model update. However, some applications, including electric load forecasting, can have different data structures which are not identically distributed on every FL client. This is also known as the domain shift problem [15].

Transfer learning techniques have been used to address the domain shift problem. However, classical transfer learning techniques require the exchange of target data [15] and are therefore undesirable for load forecasting when considering data protection regulations.

The domain shift problem has the additional downside that, in a similar way to the centralized approach, the FL model needs to learn the different data structures of each client or face the downside of an overall decreased model performance.

[13,25] showed that FL for short term electric load forecast is possible and can achieve similar results to SOTA centralized models. Therefore, this study assumes for all further experiments, that there are common data structures between the different clients, which federated learning is able to capture.

3.3. Alternative II: Model personalization

An alternative training method to federated learning is the personalized method (PS). PS trains a local (and unique) model for each client. Conventional model personalization is usually performed in a centralized manner, whereby all client models are trained in one central location. This not only requires increased centralized computational resources, since multiple models have to be trained in parallel, but also suffers from the same privacy and security issues as the CENT training method (c.f. Section 3.4), as both versions transmit sensitive user data. The PS approach is motivated by the new generation smart meters, featuring more computational on-edge resources, which allow the network training to occur on the device itself (c.f. Fig. 3). This alleviates both security and data privacy issues, while also avoiding any centralized model training as no user data is transmitted.

Another benefit of this localized training is the simplification of the prediction task, because the model only needs to learn the structures of one data source. This also solves the domain shift problem of FL, as each PS model is allowed to converge to its own optima, therefore not requiring identically distributed data across all clients. Model personalization was analyzed by [18] to solve the problem of different data sources. They successfully retrained centralized models on user-specific data, without any further exchange with the centralized model, to allow the personalized model to be optimized by the specific user data structure. [13] also showed an improved performance of a personalized model, compared to a conventional centralized approach.

This paper thus investigates PS as an alternative method to FL for the training of decentralized models.

3.4. Conventional method I: Centralized training

As described above, the centralized method (CENT) collects and aggregates load data at a centralized point to train one global model. However, as this transmission of private user data is prohibited without a specific agreement from the end user, the CENT approach was only implemented to benchmark the FL and PS methods.

3.5. Conventional method II: Pretrained baseline

To have another means of comparison for all previously described methods, this study used the baseline method (BASE) (Fig. 3). The BASE model consists of the same TCN predictor as the other training methods, however it emulates the traditional pretrained predictor approach, where a model is trained only on previously available data, and then used for inference only on new and unknown households. To simulate this behavior, the BASE model is trained on one subset of households $S_{BASE_{TRAIN}}$ and then evaluated on an entirely different subset of households $S_{BASE_{VAL}}$. To maintain comparability of results, the evaluation subset used in BASE is the same as used for all other methods.

$$S_{BASE_{TRAIN}} = \{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n\} \notin S_{BASE_{VAL}} \quad (3)$$

$$S_{BASE_{VAL}} = S_{VAL} \quad (4)$$

4. Comparison of training methods

The goal of this paper is to analyze and compare the different training methods described in Section 3. A simulation approach was implemented to allow for a repeatable experiment with different data sources which enables a statistical relevant comparison of the different training methods.

4.1. Simulation pre-processing

The pre-processing steps for the simulation included:

- Pre-processing of the dataset (c.f. Section 4.1.1), and
- Selection of the model hyperparameters (c.f. Section 4.1.2).

4.1.1. The data preparations

The Low Carbon London (LCL) dataset [26] was used for all experiments within the simulation. The LCL dataset is a publicly available set of smart meter readings collected in the London area. It is dated between 2012 and 2014 and contains individual load curves from 5566 households with an average time span of 1.73 years at a resolution of 30 min. The following pre-processing steps were applied to the LCL dataset to reduce the chances of over-fitting on seasonal effects, avoid giving unwanted preference to certain households within the dataset, and to prevent the model from accidentally using test data during training:

- Removal of duplicate entries,
- Forward filling of single missing time stamp values,
- Selection of all households with a 13 months time frame (365 + 31 days per household), with data availability $\geq 99.5\%$ (5082 households remaining),
- Order selected dataset according to start day,
- Splitting of the dataset into 13 groups of 366 households, with each household having a different starting day through the year, to reduce seasonal effects within one group,
- Reserving three groups as a hold out dataset for future tests (3660 households remaining),
- Splitting of each remaining household into training-, validation-, and test-set according to the lower part of Fig. 5, to be able to train, validate and test on the same data structure, and
- Re-scaling of data with per-house-standardization.

Table 1

Optimal Hyperparameters determined by HyperBand Search.

Parameter	Optima
Data Input Length I_w	5 days
Prediction Length O_w	1 day
Nr of parallel TCN Filter	64
Nr of TCN layers	8
Dilation of TCN layers	2
TCN Dropout rate	0.1
Regularization	L1 0.0001
Normalization Function	per LCL house standardization scaling
Use Time of Day as Input	No
Use Day of Week as Input	No
Nr. of Parameters of Model	760,800

4.1.2. Model tuning

An optimization step was performed on the hyperparameters of the TCN architecture to have a good starting point for the simulation. This optimization employed the Bayesian optimization HyperBand Search (TuneBOHB) [27] in combination with the corresponding scheduler (HyperBandForBOHB) from the RAY Tune library [28]. The optimization target was the minimization of the validation loss calculated using the mean absolute error. Each iteration of the optimization employed a set of randomly selected households as the data source for the model. The optimized hyperparameters, and their best choices, are summarized in Table 1. Unless stated differently, each subsequent experiment implies the use of the optimal parameters evaluated during this model tuning step.

4.1.3. Definition of simulation structure

Additional hyperparameters were defined in order to establish the simulation framework, specifically:

- Number of simultaneously trained clients for each training method,
- Number of epochs upon which the models are trained,
- Number of training steps per epoch, and
- Number of experiment repetitions (with different household compositions).

The values of these parameters were chosen to represent an upcoming field trial linked to this research where load forecasting on 30 houses will be tested. Therefore, the following client numbers were defined for each experiment-run:

- 30 Baseline Clients (BASE)
 - 1 Centralized Client (CENT)
- 30 Federated Learning Clients (FL-C)
 - 1 Federated Learning Server (FL-S)
- 30 Personalization Clients (PS)

Note that although it is possible to initialize 30 FL and PS clients, the CENT and FL-Server could only be initialized once per experiment-run as the FL and PS clients were only ever trained on one household, whereas the FL-Server and the CENT model are trained on the collection of the 30 households. Although the BASE models were also trained on a collection of households, their training data did not include any of the households which were used within the other training methods, as to simulate a pretrained model with no prior information of these “new” households (c.f. Section 3.5). Thus, it was possible to train 30 BASE clients per experiment and test them all on the same 30 test-households from the other solution methods.

The number of steps per epoch was set to 10 to comply with the restrictions of the FL process, as FL only works when there are frequent updates of the model weights between all the models.

Fig. 5. Train/Validation/Test split of LCL dataset.

Flowchart	Internal Steps					
Setup Experiments	Create List of Experiments (LoE) with all Experiment Parameters					
For n experiments:	Read Parameters from n-th Entry in LoE					
Start Experiment	Description	Base	Centralized	Personalized	Federated	
Setup of all Clients (With Params from LoE)	Generate Clients	Base 1 .. k B ₁ ... B _k	1 Cent Client Cent 1	PS Clients 1 ... N PS 1 ... PS n	FL Server FL-S	FL Clients 1 ... n FLC-1 ... FLC-N
	Initialize (with households H)	H _M ... H _{M+K}	H ₁ ... H _N	H ₁ ... H _N	No Data on device Only connects with Clients	H ₁ ... H _N
For n_r Rounds:	Start Round i	Train on all M ... M+K houses For e epochs	Train on all 1 ... N houses For e epochs	Train on one house For e epochs	No training	Train on one house each For e epochs
Model Training + Evaluation	Evaluate Clients	Evaluate on each of 1 .. N Houses Plot Prediction	Evaluate on each of 1 .. N Houses Plot Prediction	Evaluate on specific house Plot Prediction	Plot Prediction	Evaluate on specific house Plot Prediction
	Fed Avg Step				Avg all over FL Clients Weights Evaluate Server	Recieve & Update Weights
End Experiment	Cleanup etc.	Close all clients, save all results and params in separate JSON files				
End Simulation						

Fig. 6. Flowchart of simulation process for training method comparisons.

The number of total epochs was set to 500 based on the convergence behavior of all models, resulting in all models fully converging before the end of one experiment-run.

The experiments were repeated 100 times with different household compositions to have enough samples for a statistically relevant analysis of the performance results of the different training methods.

4.2. Simulation procedure

To have comparable results, all clients of the different training methods need to be evaluated on the same LCL households. For this, the PS, FL and CENT methods are all trained, evaluated, and tested on the same subset of 30 households. However, the BASE method is only tested on this set of 30 households and trained on a different set of 30 households as to imitate a pretrained-model approach. The complete simulation procedure is visualized in Fig. 6.

4.3. Hypothesis

A hypothesis was formulated for the performance rank of the different training methods. This hypothesis was made under the assumption that all analyzed methods have the same model architecture and thus the same number of parameters. This means that, in theory, the simpler the problem a certain method has to solve, the better the expected

Table 2

Hypothesis of performance ranking of training methods.					
Training Method	PS	CENT	FL-C	FL-S	BASE
Performance Rank	1	2	3 ^a	3 ^a	4

^aToo similar to be considered different.

performance of the given method would be. With this expectation, the hypothesis shown in Table 2 was formulated.

Under the aforementioned assumptions, it was expected that the PS approach would perform best among all solution methods. This is because, in theory, the PS approach has the simplest problem to solve as it only needs to learn one user's behavior. The CENT approach was expected to have the second-best performance, as while it has a more complex problem to solve than the PS approach, it can exclusively make use of gradient descent to find a local optima of its network parameters, in comparison to the relatively naive process of node wise averaging employed by FL. Therefore, it was expected that the FL process would have a slightly lower performance. Note that although this study differentiates between the FL-sub-types of FL-Client (FL-C) and FL-Server (FL-S), it was expected for the two sub-types to perform the same as they will experience a regular equalization (FedAvg step). Lastly, it was expected for the BASE method to perform the worst

Fig. 7. Comparison of the different distributions of test loss of each training methods.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the converged test loss of all training methods trained on the same data.

because it is trained on a different set of households and thus should not learn the structure of the test-dataset as well as the other methods.

5. Simulation results

In this section, the results of the simulations defined in Section 4 are presented and discussed.

Correct implementation of the simulation and all training methods were verified by observing of a convergence during training behavior and by validating prediction plots against target values (such as that observed in Fig. 1).

5.1. Initial comparison of results: The influence of load data

When the absolute loss distributions of the different training methods were first compared, loss values were observed to be similar across all training methods (Fig. 7). However, overall the distributions also show a wide variance in performance across all the different analyzed households. For example, the adjusted error for the centralized model was observed to be between 0 and 6, whereas the adjusted error for the personalized model was observed to be between 0 and 13 (see Fig. 7).

A hypothesis was formulated that the main contributor influencing the models' performance was the form of training data, rather than the training method itself. This could lead to incorrect conclusions being reached regarding the most performant training method based on the (data dominated) performance values alone.

To verify that the difference in performance was dominated by a change in data source rather than a change in training method, further analysis was performed, with the results being presented in Fig. 8. The plot visualizes the distribution of losses of a small number of houses across all training methods in order to highlight the underlying data source responsible for each logged loss value. Each dot in the figure represents a model test loss. The color of the dot designates its data source, its position on the X-axis corresponds to the training method and its position of the Y-axis equals the loss magnitude. For ease of comprehension, data from only two households is shown. The figure with all households from the small sample set was moved to Appendix (c.F. Fig. A.11).

In Fig. 8 it can be observed that:

- the losses from each individual household are clustered together within each training method,
- the house clusters are distinct from each other, and
- the distribution of losses are similar for a given house across all training methods, whereas large differences can be observed between different houses within the same training method.

This indicates that the main difference in loss stems from the difference in data source, rather than difference in performance of the training methods. The same conclusion can be drawn from the fact that the same houses lead to similar loss values across all training methods, whereas different houses create considerable differences in loss within

Fig. 9. Test loss results of different training methods analyzed by [9].

one training method. Our results indicate that a comparison only of the distribution of losses will in fact constitute a comparison of data structures, rather than a comparison of the performance of training methods, and should therefore not be used to select the best performing method.

Note that these results were gathered under the constraint of only using normalized load values. Additionally, a similar behavior could be observed when a relative loss function, such as the MAPE, was used. A possible solution to the problem of data variance is proposed in Section 5.2.

On further analysis, evidence of this effect was observed in the existing body of literature. For example, [9] analyzed and compared federated learning, model personalization (called Individual LSTM within their work), and a centralized model. They compared the different MAPE losses generated by these different training methods (Fig. 9). In their comparison, it is can be observed that the loss from different training methods is impacted by the difference in the data source. For example, all training methods performed well on House 6, whereas they all performed poorly on House 13.

5.2. Reducing the influence of load data using differential comparison

A method was required to mitigate the influence of source data to properly evaluate the relative performance of the forecasting models. This section describes various options and explains the approach that was used in subsequent simulations.

There are several ways to evaluate model performance while reducing the influence of the source data. The first is to normalize the input and target data used for training, validation, and testing. A normalization, however, still keeps large load swings within the dataset intact, which in turn means that the problem of the data variance (or data influence) cannot be solved in its entirety.

A second way to mitigate the influence of the data is to use a loss which is less affected by the scale of the different data sources. [9] uses the MAPE loss to justify a comparison between the different training methods. However, the MAPE loss only compensates for offsets in loss and not for internal variance, thus the data influence problem can still persist.

A third option to reduce the effects of the data on the loss distribution is to always use the same training data when evaluating

the different models. However, as described in Section 5.1, while this reduces the effects of the data, it does not entirely eliminate them.

This paper thus proposes an alternative to solve the data influence problem that involves directly comparing the differences between the losses of the different clients on each individual sample from each data source (household) across all investigated models. This is ideal for electric load forecasting as it allows for the subtraction of the effects caused by the difference in data sources. This cancels out the different data source-influences on the distribution, making the comparison more accurate and significant. This is achieved by subtracting the losses of two training methods which are trained on the same data sample, effectively removing the influence of the data source DS (Eqs. (5)–(8)).

$$L_{PS} = L_{DS} + L_{\Delta PS} \tag{5}$$

$$L_{FL-C} = L_{DS} + L_{\Delta FL-C} \tag{6}$$

$$[L_{FL-C} - L_{PS}] = L_{\Delta PS} - L_{\Delta FL-C} \tag{7}$$

Where L_{PS} and L_{FL} are the losses of the PS and the FL training methods respectively. Resulting in a more significant difference between the two methods:

$$\left| \frac{L_{\Delta FL-C}}{L_{\Delta PS}} \right| \gg \left| \frac{L_{FL-C}}{L_{PS}} \right| \tag{8}$$

*assumption for this behavior : $L_{PS} < L_{FL}$

Using this differential comparison, it is possible to build a distribution of differences between two training methods (as seen in the example of Fig. 10) as long as the two methods were trained on the same datasets using identical evaluation samples.

To be able to properly compare all training methods with each other and to evaluate the best performing one, this study combined:

- Data standardization of model input and model output,
- Validation and test of all models on identical datasets,
- Differential comparison of all training methods and data sources in a pairwise comparison (example in Fig. 10), and
- Summation of all means of differences (Table 3).

Fig. 10. Differential comparison result comparison of FL-C and PS.

Table 3

Mean of distribution of differences from differential comparisons with adjusted error.

Loss Diff [y - x]	PS	CENT	FL-C	FL-S	BASE
PS	0	0.0421	0.0459	0.0459	0.0512
CENT	-0.0421	0	0.0038	0.0038	0.0091
FL-C	-0.0459	-0.0038	0	0.0001	0.0053
FL-S	-0.0459	-0.0038	0.0001	0	0.0053
BASE	-0.0512	-0.0091	-0.0053	-0.0053	0
Sum	-0.1851	0.0254	0.0443	0.0445	0.0709
Rank	1	2	3 ^a	3 ^a	4

Negative Loss Difference = Better Performance of vertical Solution Method.

^aDifference too similar to be considered different ranks.

5.3. Statistical comparison

Table 3 verifies that the personalized method (PS) has the best performance among the different training methods. It is followed by the CENT method, then the FL-Client and -Server methods and lastly the BASE method.

Further, a statistical analysis of the differential comparison was made in order to calculate the certainty of this ranking and to be able to either reject or accept the hypothesis made in Section 4.3. The differential comparison was used to count the number of times a certain training method was better than the other training methods. All pairwise comparison within a training method were then summed up (*Sum*) and used to calculate relative superiority rate of each method. Note that an equal performance of all training methods would lead to a superiority rate around 50% with a $Sum \approx 0$.

The comparisons in Table 4 show that, in a direct comparison, the PS method is superior to all other training methods in 59.1% of cases. Considering the confidence of this test being greater than 3σ confidence level, the result is recognized as a significant difference in performance. Therefore, this paper recommends model personalization (PS) as the training method of choice when applying load forecasting on new and previously unknown data structures.

In an isolated comparison between the remaining training methods, the results show that the CENT method is superior to the FL and BASE methods in 55.1% of cases. This again is a significant difference with a confidence $> 3\sigma$.

If only the FL and BASE methods are compared with each other, the results show that in 52% of cases, both the FL-S and the FL-C are better

than the BASE method with a significant confidence $> 3\sigma$. However, the differences between the FL-C and FL-S are not large enough for them to be considered significantly different. All these observed results are in line with hypothesis made in Section 4.3 which can thus be accepted.

5.4. Summary of results

The results of the analysis and performance comparison of the training methods explored in this study are summarized in the following four points:

- Identification of data influence as a problem when comparing loss distributions of training methods using different data source sets (data influence is the dominant factor).
- Development of a differential comparison allowing for the isolation of the differences caused by the training methods.
- Evaluation of model personalization (PS) as the best performing model training method among the four analyzed methods.
- Shows that the analyzed training method alternatives (PS, FL) both have a better performance than the pretrained baseline method (BASE).

6. Conclusion

This study analyzed training method alternatives for load forecasting based on neural networks. The work was motivated by a hypothesis that distributed approaches to model training offer enhanced privacy

Table 4
Comparison of superiority count from differential comparison.

Sum Count [y vs. x]	PS	CENT	FL-C	FL-S	BASE
PS	0	-12344	-18304	-18348	-19444
CENT	12344	0	-8388	-8324	-12264
FL-C	18304	8388	0	200	-5864
FL-S	18348	8324	-200	0	-6180
BASE	19444	12264	5864	6180	0
Sum	68480	16632	-26692	-20292	-43752
Relative Superiority Rate	0.591	0.522	0.472	0.473	0.442
Rank	1	2	3 ^a	3 ^a	4
Hypothesis	1	2	3 ^a	3 ^a	4

Comparisons: Add +1 to count if method is better, -1 if method is worse.

^aDifference too similar to be considered different ranks.

Fig. A.11. Comparison of all training methods trained on the same source data.

and security for end-user data as they avoid centralization of electric load data. It compared the methods of model personalization (PS) and federated learning (FL) to the conventional use of a centralized predictor and a pretrained baseline within an extensive simulation. In the simulation, a Temporal Convolutional Network was trained on a single household and optimized on an adjusted error loss function to do short-term electric load forecasting.

During the results analysis this study identified that the specific characteristics of the load curve data are a dominant factor when comparing model performances on a multi-client dataset, in particular the statistical and relative distribution of load curve peaks, and the difference in scale of load curve samples. If disregarded, this problem could lead to an accidental comparison of data, rather than a comparison of model performance. As a solution, this study proposes the method of “differential comparison” to isolate the changes in performance to the changes in training method or model type, providing a more secure comparison of performances when comparing losses based on multiple data sources. This is achieved by only ever comparing the loss differences of the exact same data sample across all investigated models. This allows for the subtraction of the loss offsets caused by the difference in data structure.

With the method of differential comparison, the study identified PS as the superior training method among the analyzed training methods in 59.1 % of all cases. This performance difference has a significance greater than 3σ . Additionally this study finds that the four analyzed training methods all have statistically relevant performance differences with a significance level greater 3σ . Their ranking is described in [Table 5](#).

As model personalization showed both the best performance among the evaluated methods, is in line with data privacy regulations, and does not suffer from the domain shift problem, this study recommends model personalization as the training method of choice for short-term electric load forecasting.

Table 5
Performance ranking of all analyzed training methods.

Training Method	PS	CENT	FL	BASE
Rank	1	2	3	4

6.1. Transfer learning option for future federated learning

Federated learning works optimally when all client data is independent and identically distributed, but this is not always the case for electric load forecasting. In literature the common solution to this problem is to use transfer learning; however, classical transfer learning requires the transmission of the target values from client to client. This is not in line with data privacy regulations that typically govern electric load data. Therefore transfer learning was not pursued within this study. In 2022, [15] published a new transfer learning method, with the condition that the raw data of different clients cannot be communicated, in order to preserve data privacy. Within their study they show promising results for industrial federated transfer learning problems in machine maintenance.

We acknowledge that a repetition of the federated learning experiments with transfer learning could lead to more promising results regarding the FL performance. However as model personalization does not suffer from the domain shift problem, this study still recommends PS as the model training method of choice for short-term electric load forecasting.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fabian Widmer: Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Severin Nowak:** Writing – review & editing. **Benjamin Bowler:** Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Patrick Huber:** Data curation, Resources. **Antonios Papaemmanouil:** Funding acquisition, Review, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Antonios Papaemmanouil reports financial support was provided by Swiss Federation of Energy (SFOE).

Data availability

The used LCL dataset is a publicly available dataset [26]

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Appendix. Full figures

This section contains un-zoomed figures used within the main part of this study (see Fig. A.11).

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